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Digitization of natural collections – the way to immortality

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Annotation: Оцифрування – це невідворотне майбутнє усіх природничих колекцій. На сьогодні не викликає сумніву і запитань необхідність оцифрування, особливо якщо це стосується рідкісних чи унікальних зразків, або ж малих колекцій, які наражені на найбільшу небезпеку зникнення. Якщо питання як і що саме оцифрувати залежить від спеціалістів окремих груп, то питання де і які дані згодом зберігати викликає чимало дискусій.

Keywords: *biodata, virtual collections, digitization, data providers, data aggregators.*

Ключові слова: *біодані, віртуальні колекції, оцифрування, провайдери, агрегат ори.*

It is even hard to estimate general circumscription of natural history collections. Comprehensive database GRSciColl lists 1,095 collections from 7,522 registered institutions across the world (Schindel et al. 2016). From 1.2 to 3 billions of specimens are suggested to be preserved in those collections (Ariño 2010, Vollmar et al. 2010). If follow another database, Index Herbariorum, 3,095 herbaria are registered for today in the world, and contain about 390 million specimens (Thiers 2019). However even this quite narrow fetch limited by plants is far away from real state of things. In 2019 Index Herbariorum listed for Ukraine only 23 herbaria with about 4 millions of specimens, while more precise investigation from 2011 already declared 59 herbarium collections with more than 4,3 millions of specimens (Shiyan 2011).

This testifies to the fact that there are still a lot of natural history collections hidden from us due to different reasons. Despite the fact that most important collections are well known and mainly included in databases at different level, small collections still contains important, sometimes even unique, vouchers. Absence of data from those collections in free access makes them higher endangered, because they remain to persist out of focus of scientific and public community and finally can be lost. Digitization of natural collections provides number of benefits including increased visibility and, as a result, higher enrolment of specimens in scientific research (Holovachov et al. 2014, Cantrill 2018). Of course, entries of virtual collections cannot replace original specimens, but they definitely amplify them and provide new opportunity for distribution of data (Drew 2011). In case of small collections that have a lack of financial support, imperfect

conditions for preservation of specimens, and general dubious future, digitization, perhaps, is the only way to survive in form digital data.

Digitization can be subdivided on two main stages, which can be either realized simultaneously or subsequently. First – data capturing (i.e., creation of datasets representing information about specimens) and second – imaging (obtaining of digital picture of the specimens). Third stage, data distribution, is usually considered separately. However, both data capturing and imaging are strictly depended from purposes and structure of final database. Major data aggregators like GBIF work only with standard protocols, and it is quite important to remember about this before start of digitization. In most cases data are gathered and distributed under Darwin Core and ABCD standards (Blum et al. 2019). There are few other standards, but all of them are based on experience of number of previous workflows, complications and mistakes, so it is always better to follow an accepted standard than to create your own insight. Some of standards can be partly or fully cross-changed, and in general follow the same principles, among which data completeness, data usability/reproduction, and data quality. Data quality is main and crucial aspect in digitization and today most of institutions prefer to obtain high-quality images of limited number of selected specimens accompanied by high quality data rather to simply digitize everything without control of qualified specialists (Blagoderov et al. 2012). Low-quality data are not simply useless, even worse – they can result in scientific misinterpretations (Ferro and Flick 2015, Sikes et al. 2016) that are almost impossible to reveal after publication.

Hence, I believe that digitization of natural collections in Ukraine is necessary step that should be realized in frames of previous experience and following accepted standards. Creation of local or national databases with internal protocols that have no opportunity to export data to global aggregators is rather dead end neither attempts to assert our national identity. Local databases usually contain more precise information and have extra facilities for narrow specialist; however without intermediation with global aggregators they stay isolated and finally doomed to extinction. From other hand, global aggregators should improve the trust of scientific community by change of general paradigm of data providers and developing of new integrated protocols of data annotation (Franz and Beckett 2018).

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Наукове видання

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